

The Transformation of Workers from Unstable to Stable in the Italian Regions

Between 2013 and 2019, the transformation of workers from unstable to stable in Italy increased by a value of 1.65 units.

Ranking of regions by transformation of workers from unstable to stable. Istat calculates the transformation of unstable jobs into stable jobs in the Italian regions and macro-regions. The first place for the value of the transformation from unstable to stable works is Veneto with an amount equal to 32.50, followed by Lombardy with an amount equal to 31.40 and Tuscany with an amount equal to 27.20. In the middle of the table there are Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount equal to 21.00, Sardinia with a value equal to 19.90 and Liguria with a value equal to 19.00. Puglia closes the ranking with a value of 11.20, the Aosta Valley with a value of 10.70 and Calabria with a value of 9.20 units.

Change in the Transformation of Unstable Jobs into Stable Between 2013 and 2019. If we take into account the absolute change between 2013 and 2019, it is possible to reformulate the ranking based on the transformation of unstable workers into stable. In first place there is Veneto with an amount equal to 12.2 units, followed by Tuscany with a value equal to 9.1 units and Lombardy with an amount equal to 8.2 units. In the middle of the table there are Umbria with a value equal to 1.3 units followed by Campania with an amount of 1.2 units and Piedmont equal to 1.1 units. Sardinia closes the ranking with a value of -4 units, followed by Lazio with an amount of -4.3 units and Valle d'Aosta with a value of -9.1 units.

Veneto. The value of transformations from unstable jobs to buildings in Veneto increased in the period between 2013 and 2019 by an amount equal to 12.2 units or equal to a value of 60.09%. In 2013, the value of the transformation of unstable works into buildings in Veneto was equal to an amount of 20.3 units. Subsequently, between 2013 and 2014, this value decreased from an amount of 20.3 units to a value of 19.1 units or equal to a change of -1.2 units equal to -5.91%. In the transition between 2014 and 2015 the value of the transformation of unstable and stable workers increased from 19.1 units up to a value of 19.2 units or equal to a value of 0.1 units equal to an amount of 0.524 %. Between 2015 and 2015 the value of transformations from unstable to stable jobs increased from an amount equal to 19.2 units up to a value of 22.9 units or equal to a variation of 3.7 units equal to a amount of 19.27%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the value of transformations from unstable to stable jobs decreased, in Veneto, from an amount equal to 22.9 units or by a value equal to 3.7 units up to a value of 19, 27%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the transformation of unstable and stable works decreased from an amount equal to 22.9 units up to a value equal to 17.7 units or equal to a change of -5.2 units equal to an amount of 22.71%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of the transformation of unstable workers into stable workers increased from an amount equal to 17.7 units up to a value equal to 23.4 units or equal to an amount of 5.7 units equal at a value of 32.2%. In the transition between 2018 and 2019, the value of transformations from unstable to stable jobs increased from a value of 23.4 units to a value of 32.5 units or equal to a value of 9.1 units equal to an amount of 38.89%.

Italy. The transformation of unstable jobs into stable jobs in Italy grew in the period between 2013 and 2019 by a value of 3.3 units or equal to a variation of 17.83%. In 2013 the value of the

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transformation of unstable works in Italy was equal to a value of 18.5 and in the following year it decreased to a value of 16.6 units or equal to a reduction of -1.9 units equal to -10.27%. Between 2014 and 2015 the value of the transformation of unstable jobs into stable jobs increased from an amount equal to 16.6 units up to a value equal to 18.4 units or equal to a variation of 1.8 units equal to a amount of 10.84%. Between 2015 and 2016 the value of the transformation of unstable jobs into stable jobs in Italy increased from a value of 18.4 units to a value of 21.3 units or equal to a change of 2.9 units equal at a variation of 15.76%. Between 2016 and 2017, the value of the transformation of unstable to stable workers decreased from an amount equal to 21.3 units to a value of 15.8 units or equal to a change of -5.5 units equal to a value of -25.82%. Between 2017 and 2018, the value of transformations from unstable workers to permanent workers in Italy decreased from a value of 15.8 units to a value of 15 units or equal to a change of -0.8 units equal to an amount of -5.06%. Between 2018 and 2019 the transformation of unstable jobs into stable jobs increased from an amount equal to 15 units up to a value of 21.8 units or equal to a variation of 6.8 units or equal to a variation of 45.3%.

Conclusions. The transformation of unstable workers into stable is a measure of the efficiency and dynamism of the local labor market. This value is high in Northern Italy, or equal to 5.4 units, low in the South or equal to 1.6 units, and in the Center equal to 0.6 units. The low ability to transform unstable jobs into stable jobs indicates a high degree of precariousness. Excess of work flexibility can lead to an increase in the number of poor people and working poors. Working poors are low-income workers who persist in poverty even in the absence of unemployment. Unstable workers are part of the phenomenon of financial fragility which also affects the employed. The worsening of the conditions of the employed reduces the confidence of the population in the possibility of emancipation through work. Economic labor policies through fiscal incentives for stable forms of work must also be accompanied by adequate income growth. In fact, income growth makes work a tool for economic and social elevation and can increase the activism of the population with positive effects on GDP, on the reduction of inequality, and on social cohesion.

Declarations

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